

University, Aligarh, for providing research facilities and C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance to one of us (R.A.).

References

1. E. E. RIED, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1900, **24**, 397.
2. T. C. BRUCE and D. W. TANNER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, **30**, 1668.
3. R. AHMAD, M. N. KHAN and A. A. KHAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14A**, 807.
4. M. N. KHAN, R. AHMAD and A. A. KHAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14A**, 961.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis." (Longmans, Green London), 1955, p. 643.
6. F. KAUFER, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1906, **55**, 502.
7. S. ROVIRA, *Ann. Chim.*, 1945, **20**, 660.
8. C. A. BUNTON, B. NAYAK and C. J. O'CONNOR, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, **33**, 572.
9. M. L. BENDER, R. D. GINGER and K. C. KEMP, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 3350; 1958, **80**, 1044.
10. F. YOKOYAMA, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1943, **63**, 5.
11. C. H. HALB, M. N. HALB and W. H. JONES, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, **21**, 1549.
12. K. R. LYNN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 687.
13. C. A. BUNTON, S. J. FARBER, A. J. MILBANK, C. J. O'CONNOR and T. A. TURNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, Perkin II, 1972, 1869.
14. K. J. LAIDLER, "Chemical Kinetics", (McGraw-Hill, New York), 1965, 53, 89.
15. M. L. BENDER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 5986.
16. M. L. BENDER and R. D. GINGER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 348.
17. S. S. RIECHLER and R. W. TAFT (JR.), *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 4927.
18. P. M. MADER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 3191.
19. D. BROOKE and D. E. GUTTMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 4964.

Azine Dyes as Redox Indicators in Dichrometry*

N. VENKATESWARA RAO and K. M. M. KRISHNA PRASAD

Andhra University, Waltair-530003

Manuscript received 1 February 1978, revised 27 July 1978, accepted 22 December 1978

THE use of azine dyes as redox indicators in dichrometry has not been reported till now. In continuation of our recent studies on the use of some azine dyes as cerimetric redox indicators¹, we have examined the suitability of six azine dyes, Phenosafranine (PS), Methylene Violet (MV), Amethyst Violet (AV), Safranin T (ST), Wool Fast Blue BL (WFBBL) (Colour Index Nos. 50200, 50210, 50225, 50240 and 50315 respectively) and Aposafranine (AS), having the following structures, as indicators in the dichrometric titrations of iron(II), hexacyanoferrate(II), arsenic(III), uranium(IV), molybdenum(V) and hydroquinone in media of sulphuric,

hydrochloric, perchloric and phosphoric acids. Our studies have shown that the titrations of iron(II), uranium(IV) and molybdenum(V) are feasible in sulphuric, hydrochloric and perchloric acids but not in phosphoric acid medium, whereas titrations of hexacyanoferrate(II), arsenic(III) and hydroquinone are not possible in any acid medium.

Experimental

0.1 N solutions of iron(II), uranium(IV), and molybdenum(V) were prepared and standardised. 0.1 N solution of potassium dichromate was also prepared.

0.1% solutions of the dyes were prepared in deionised water. Wool Fast Blue BL was Bayer sample and the other five dyes were Gurr samples.

Phenosafranine : R₁=R₄=H; R₂=R₃=NH₂.
C. I. No. 50200

Methylene Violet : R₁=R₄=H; R₂=NH₂; R₃=N(CH₃)₂.
C. I. No. 50210

Amethyst Violet : R₁=R₄=H; R₂=R₃=N(C₂H₅)₂.
C. I. No. 50225

Safranin T : R₁=R₄=CH₃; R₂=R₃=NH₂.
C. I. No. 50240

Aposafranine : R₁=R₂=R₄=H; R₃=NH₂.

Wool Fast Blue BL
C. I. No. 50315

Other chemicals used were of reagent grade quality.

* Presented at the 65th Session of the Indian Science Congress, Ahmedabad, January 3-7, 1978.

General Procedure :

4 to 10 ml of the reductant solution is treated with enough 1 : 1 H_2SO_4 , HCl or $HClO_4$ (70%) so as to give the required acid concentration and the solution is diluted to 50 ml. 0.1 ml (0.2 ml with WFBBL) of 0.1% PS, MV, AV, ST or AS is added and the mixture titrated with the dichromate solution. The colour changes obtained are sharp and these, along with the conditions of titration, are mentioned in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - CONDITIONS OF TITRATIONS AND COLOUR CHANGES AT THE END POINTS

Indicator	Conditions and end point colour changes		
	H_2SO_4, M	HCl, M	$HClO_4, M$
<u>Titration of Iron (II)</u>			
PS	1.0-5.0 ; green to violet.	1.5-3.0 ; greenish yellow to bright orange red.	2.0-4.0+3 ml H_2PO_4 ; blue to violet.
MV	0.5-1.0 ; α, β bluish violet to pink.	1.0-3.0 ; green to yellow.	2.0-4.0+3 ml H_2PO_4 ; green to pink.
AV	1.0-3.0 ; α bluish green to violet.	1.0-3.0 ; green to orange.	2.0-4.0+3 ml H_2PO_4 ; blue to pink.
ST	1.0-5.0 ; bluish green to violet.	1.5-3.0 ; green to yellow.	2.0-4.0+3 ml H_2PO_4 ; bluish green to parrot green.
WFBBL	(a)	(a)	3.0-4.0+3 ml H_2PO_4 ; blue to pink.
AS	0.5-2.0 ; α, β violet to pink.	1.5-3.0 ; green to yellow.	2.0-4.0+3 ml H_2PO_4 ; blue to green.
<u>Titration of Uranium(IV)</u>			
PS	2.0-4.0 ; blue (or light green) to pink.	1.5-3.5 ; ϵ pale green to bright pink.	(a)
MV	1.0-2.0 ; green to colourless.	1.0-2.0 ; ϵ bluish green (or pale green) to pink.	(a)
AV	1.0-2.0 ; violet to bright pink.	2.0-4.0 ; ϵ pale green to pink.	(a)
ST	1.0-2.0 ; pale pink to pale yellow.	(a)	(a)
WFBBL	1.0-1.5 ; blue to light green.	(a)	(a)
AS	1.0-2.0 ; ϵ greenish blue to pale parrot green.	(a)	(a)
<u>Titration of Molybdenum(V)</u>			
PS	—	1.5-3.0 ; blue to pink.	—
MV	—	1.5-3.0 ; pale green to pink.	(a)
AV	—	1.5-3.0 ; blue to pink.	2.0-3.0 ; blue to violet.
ST	—	2.0-3.0 ; violet to pink.	—
WFBBL	—	(a)	—
AS	—	2.0-3.0 ; blue to pink.	—

$\alpha = +10$ ml of 0.1M Fe(III) solution. $\beta =$ Indicator should be added near the end point.

(a) = Titration is not possible. $\epsilon = +0.5$ ml of 0.01M V(IV) solution.

In titrations of iron(II) in sulphuric acid medium employing MV, AV and AS as indicators, the oxidation of these indicators by dichromate is slow and is accelerated by iron(III). Hence the titrations with these indicators have to be performed in presence of 10 ml of 0.1M iron(III) solution.

While titrating uranium(IV), the oxidant should be added dropwise near the end point, waiting for about 10-15 sec after each addition. The end point is not sharp in titrations involving more than 0.3 m moles of uranium(IV).

Titrations of molybdenum(V) have to be conducted in presence of 0.5 ml of 0.01M V(IV) solution while using PS, MV, AV, and AS and 1 ml of 0.01M V(IV) solution while using ST as indicators. Further, the oxidant should be added dropwise near the end point, waiting for about 10-15 sec after each addition.

The results obtained are in excellent agreement with the theoretical values.

These indicators are not suitable in titrations involving dilute (0.01N and 0.02N) solutions of the reductants with dichromate solutions of corresponding concentrations, as well as the reverse titrations, i.e., titrations of dichromate with the reductants.

No indicator correction is necessary in titrations involving 0.1N and 0.05N solutions.

The transition potentials, determined in accordance with the method of Knop², are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—TRANSITION POTENTIALS FOR IRON(II)-DICHROMATE TITRATION

Indicator	Acid medium and transition potential, mV vs N.H.E.		
	1M H_2SO_4	2M HCl	3M $HClO_4$ (+3 ml H_2PO_4)
PS	800 ± 15	950 ± 10	890 ± 10
MV	1000 ± 15 ⁺	800 ± 15	790 ± 10
AV	1010 ± 15 ⁺	905 ± 10	830 ± 10
ST	810 ± 15	1000 ± 10	910 ± 10
WFBBL	†	†	835 ± 10
AS	1000 ± 10 ⁺	900 ± 10	870 ± 10

⁺ In presence of 10 ml of 0.1M Fe(III) solution.

† WFBBL does not function satisfactorily in H_2SO_4 and HCl media.

Acknowledgement

We are grateful to the C.S.I.R. for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to K.M.M.K.P. and to the U.G.C. for financial assistance to N.V.R. and K.M.M.K.P.

References

1. N. V. RAO, K. M. M. KRISHNA PRASAD, P. V. RAMANA and K. SRIKRISHNA, 63rd Session of Indian Science Congress, Waltair, January 3-7, 1976.
2. J. KNOR, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1931, 85, 253.

Reaction of Azlactone with Aromatic Ketimines

SURINDER KUMAR, MANGAT RAI, KEWAL KRISHAN and AJIT SINGH*

Department of Chemistry, Punjabi University, Patiala

Manuscript received 18 August, 1978, accepted 22 December 1978

REACTION of azlactones, which are obtained from α -acylamido acids *in situ*, and carbonyl compounds¹ constitutes the well known Perkin reaction. Cinnamalanilines and azlactones have shown to undergo (4+2)-cycloaddition reaction². A study of this reaction with aromatic ketimines is reported in this communication.

Crystalline products were obtained by the reaction of azlactone of benzoylglycine with ketimines³ of acetophenone, *p*-bromoacetophenone and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone under Perkin conditions (acetic anhydride and sodium acetate). Elemental analysis coupled with the study of IR, NMR and mass spectra supported structures (III) assigned to the products.

IR spectrum of compound IIIa showed bands at 1750 cm^{-1} and 1670 cm^{-1} indicative of carbonyl group and C=N-linkage respectively. NMR spectrum of the compound IIIb showed three methyl protons as a singlet at 7.6 τ and nine aromatic protons as a multiplet between 2.3-2.6 τ . Mass spectrum of compound IIIc showed molecular ion peak at *m/e* 321 as the parent peak. This peak showed that acylation of OH group also took place. The M^+ ion underwent predominantly α -fission of the C-O bond of the acetyl carbonyl to yield a diradical ion $C_{13}H_{15}O_3N$ (*m/e* 278) and CH_3CO^+ (*m/e* 43). The former on decarbonylation with simultaneous elimination of C_6H_5NO as neutral species gave $C_6H_5CO^+$ ion (*m/e* 105). The latter underwent further decarbonylation to yield $C_6H_5^+$ (*m/e* 77) which showed characteristic fission of benzene nucleus. The mass spectrum also indicated the alternative C_6H_5 radical elimination to $C_{13}H_{10}O_4N^+$ ion (*m/e* 244). The mass fragmentation (Chart I) pattern of the product is consistent with its formulation as an azlactone.

The products IIIa-IIIc are found to be identical (m.m.p) with authentic samples of 2-phenyl-4-(α -methylbenzal)-5-oxazolone, 2-phenyl-4-(α -methyl-*p*-bromobenzal)-5-oxazolone and 2-phenyl-4-(α -methyl-*o*-acetoxybenzal)-5-oxazolone synthesised by an unambiguous route.

Chart-1

The formation of III is possible through the electrophilic addition of the enolate, formed by the abstraction of a proton by base from the active methylene function of the azlactone, to the ketimine to give an unstable addition compound (II). Elimination of the amine in the presence of base affords III as shown in Chart 2.

- IIIa, R = H
- IIIb, R = *p*-Br
- IIIc, R = *o*-OOCCH₃

Chart-2

Experimental

Reaction of Azlactone(I) with α -methylbenzalbenzylamine :

Benzoylglycine (0.01 mole) and α -methylbenzalbenzylamine (0.01 mole) were dissolved in dry benzene (50 ml). To this acetic anhydride (AR, 1.2 ml) and sodium acetate (0.5 g) were added. The mixture was just heated to get a clear solution and left at room temperature for 2 days. During this period